

**KOBALT (II) - NITRATE DIHYDRATE SYNTHESIS OF THE
COORDINATION COMPOUND FORMED BY QUINAZOLIN-4-ON AND
INDOLE FATTY ACIDS OF AND STUDY OF THE PROCESSES OF
INFLUENCE ON THE VARIETIES OF COTTON "BUXARA-102",
"NAMANGAN-77", "SULTAN", "UNKURGAN-1", "C-6524"**

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Annotation: Below we would like to present for the first time the coordination compound formed by quinazolin-4-on and indole fatty acids of cobalt (II)-nitrate dihydrate, the processes affecting the root-firing system of the varieties "Buxara-102", "Namangan-77", "Sultan", "Unkurgan-1", "C-6524". Prior to us, synthesis processes and biological effects were studied by individual individuals, and coordination compounds with these substances were not synthesized.

Key words: cobalt (II)-nitrate dihydrate, "Buxara-102", "Namangan-77", "Sultan", "Unkurgan-1", "C-6524" varieties, coordination compound, quinazolin-4-on and indole fatty acids, citric acid, formamide, 2,5% and 5% solutions, stimulants, physiologically active substances.

Introduction

The growth of biologically active substances favorably affects the increase in the increase in the fertility and germination capacity of seeds, accelerate the ripening of the crop, increase the resistance of the plant to drought, salinity, diseases and pests. In addition to organic additives in the composition of substances that accelerate the growth processes (stimulants, physiologically active substances), natural phytohormones are also found, these substances regulate the division and normal development of the cell in the plant, accelerate the growth of the neck of the stem, the growth of feathers and shoots and the metabolism of substances in the Leaf, enhance the The Auxin phytohormone is actively involved in the exchange of nucleic acids and proteins, which faxes the growth of roots, feathers and leaves[2-3].

In plants too, there is a messaging system similar to the nervous system of trick organisms, with a change in the concentration of phytohormones in the cell, a message comes to one or another part of the plant body. The balance of phytohormones varies in the order in which the plant grows, depending on the periods of germination, germination, flowering, end of harvest and ripening of seeds in the periods of development. During each growth period, external factors cause a certain change in the plant, changing the phytohormonal balance under the influence of cold and hot temperatures, lighting, humidity, atmospheric pressure, drought, various pathogens, pests and chemicals, and a specific reaction to external influences. That is, photosynthesis intensifies, metabolism improves, the number and weight of harvest elements increases, stress States - water deficiency, resistance to unfavorable weather conditions, as well as increased resistance to pathogens and harmful insects [4-6].

Changes in the action of hormones that occur under the influence of external stress factors (drought, salt, hot temperature, cold and the other), are controlled by biological phytohormones, which improve the mutagenic and protective system of the plant, ensuring that the physiological and genetic processes remain the same even in favorable or unfavorable conditions [7]. As a result of many years of scientific research at the Institute of cotton research of Uzbekistan, when stimulants were used before planting in seeds, the germination rate was accelerated, the root system developed energetically and it was determined that the plant absorbs more nutrients from the soil [8-12].

The synthesis of biologically active substances with the processes that affect its various plants, until now no one has been engaged in scientific work. Below, we would like to present for the first time the coordination combination of cobalt (II)-nitrate dihydrate with quinazoline-4-on and indole fatty acids, the processes affecting the root system of the varieties "Buxara-102", "Namangan-77", "Sultan", "Unkurgan-1", "C-6524" of cottons. Prior to us, synthesis processes and biological effects were studied by individual individuals, and coordination compounds with these substances were not synthesized.

The experimental part

1. Synthesis of quinazolin-4-one.

0,2 moles of o-aminobenzoic acid and 0,2 moles of formamide are put in a chemical round retort. The reaction mixture was heated in an alloy of Vudd in a reverse refrigerator for one hours at 150°C, then cooled to room temperature. When put in cold water, white crystals were formed, filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

The chemical reaction of the process is carried out as follows.

2. Effect of quinazolin-4-on with 3-indolyl fatty acid.

0,2 mol of quinazolin-4-on and 0,2 mol of 3-indolyl fatty acid are poured into a round retort. The reaction mixture was heated in a water bath in an inverted refrigerator for 3 hours at a temperature of 80-90°C, then the resulting combination is cooled to room temperature. When the formed crystals were soaked in water, yellowish crystals were formed, filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

Cobalate (II)-nitrate and quinazolin-4-one a coordinate combination of with 3-indole fatty acid.

Effect product 0,2 mol quinazolin-4-on with 3-indolyl fatty acid 0,1 mol cobalt (II)-nitrate porcelain is mixed mechanically for 3 hours with a mixer in a mortar. Every 10-15 minutes porcelain mixed is cleaned by scraping around the air and the mixer. The formula of the combination can be expressed as follows.

Our expected results in the experiment are a technique from the following stages.

1. The result of the experiment was the preparation of 2,5% and 5% li solutions of the II product in distilled water.
2. Of the 10 grains, the seeds of cotton "buxara-102", "namangan-77", "Sultan", "unkurgan-1", "C-6524" were fertilized in a 2,5% solution for 5 hours and 10 hours.
3. Seeds of cotton "buxara-102", "namangan-77", "Sultan", "unkurgan-1", "C-6524" from 10 grains of cotton were soaked for 5 hours and 10 hours in a 5% solution.

The effect of the resulting substance II on the germination of seeds.

Seeds were placed in a thermostat in a petri dish of equal four petri dishes and 1 to 10 pieces of sample, total 5 petri dishes. Temperature 27°C , humidity level 40%. For 5 hours, the ripening processes were observed in 2,5% solution compared to the ripening processes in 10% solution, for 5 hours, the ripening processes were observed in 5% solution compared to 10 hours in 10% solution. The speed of growth of the roots was carried out in this way.

It is believed that if the seeds are planted in the tubers for 2,5 hours in 5% solution to the hanging wire of the root, it is desirable to count.

In place of the conclusion, we must say that this complex coordination compound is important in biochemical processes in the organism of gooseberries, and the cobalt double valence cation in this compound is a microelement necessary for the assimilation of molecular nitrogen in the composition of atmospheric air.

In the organism of plants, a two-valence cobalt cation in the composition of the soil is insufficient in relation to the Daily need, which means that it causes its effect on the process of assimilation of nitrogen.

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